

A nonproprietary language for the command and control of cyber defenses – OpenC2

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ABSTRACT

The fact that cyber attacks are getting increasingly sophisticated and performed at machine speed motivated the development of OpenC2. This paper presents Open Command and Control (OpenC2), a suite of specifications that enable command and control of cyber defense systems and components at machine speed and in a manner that is agnostic of the underlying technologies utilized or of any other aspects of particular implementations. OpenC2 provides the means to introduce standardized interfaces to cyber defense systems, enabling interoperability and allowing seamless integration, communication, and operation between decoupled blocks that perform cyber defense functions. The suite of specifications includes a semantic language that enables machine-to-machine communication for purposes of command and control of cyber defense components, actuator profiles that specify the subset of the OpenC2 language and may extend it in the context of specific cyber defense functions, and transfer specifications that utilize existing protocols and standards to implement OpenC2 in particular environments. Fundamentally, OpenC2 addresses the acting part of the Integrated Adaptive Cyber Defense (IACD) framework and is designed to be technology agnostic, concise, abstract, and extensible. Ultimately, OpenC2 is a building block for enabling coordinated defense in cyber-relevant time, shifting traditional monolithic cyber response approaches to more granular, flexible, and adaptive.

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1. Introduction

The attack surface of cyber systems is relative to their complexity, functionality, and connectivity. Adversaries and their tactics, techniques, and procedures have become increasingly sophisticated, well-funded, and can operate at machine speed. The impact of a cyber attack can be detrimental to the well-being of a nation and the longevity of an organization whether is derived from significant financial losses and loss of intellectual property or more severe effects, such as failures in functions of critical national infrastructure that can rapidly lead to massive disruption in society and even loss of lives.

Cyber defense systems mostly operate in isolation and are often statically configured, resulting in disintegrated cybersecurity operations. As a result, investigating and responding to cybersecurity incidents, especially large-scale and sophisticated, is a non-timely and cumbersome process that provides an asymmetric time

advantage to adversaries for performing and maneuvering their attacks successfully.

Remediation and mitigation plans against cyber attacks comprise coordinated action-sets that work synergistically by utilizing multiple technologies. The integration of different cyber defense components and technologies can be expensive and requires customized communication interfaces. Such customized interfaces come in the form of application programming interfaces (APIs) that are proprietary to the parent technology. Furthermore, the functional blocks within a product may be tightly coupled with other functions and may not be directly accessible by an API, reducing the product's dynamic and integration flexibility with other tools. Overall, an integration would require middleware that translates, stores, and forwards messages between technologies. In some sense, nowadays, this is achieved by different orchestration platforms that adopt a plug and play architecture where different technologies can be integrated and interoperate. Such solutions are also difficult to scale since they depend on the availability of API hooks for the different products that the platform supports, or require developing custom interfaces for products that are not currently supported by the platform. Further, adopting

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technologies from multiple vendors undeniably introduces an extra layer of security. For example, a zero-day vulnerability that affects a specific firewall series by allowing remote code execution should not affect every firewall in an organization's infrastructure; thus, firewall-vendor diversity is desirable. Vendor diversity adds strength to an organization's infrastructure but also has its limitations. The defense is more disintegrated and makes device management more complicated and costly.

Introducing standardized function-centric interfaces for command and control enhances the ability to technologically diversify, makes device management less complicated, and simplifies integration. Also, coordinated cyber defense in cyber-relevant time requires machine-to-machine communication. A strategy that decouples the functional blocks within a cyber defense system and the definition of standardized interfaces, through a common language, for seamless communication would allow flexible integration of cyber defense components and permit incremental upgrades. An open standard language for the command and control of cyber defense systems enables interoperability between different technologies and decreases the response time to cyber attacks. For instance, an ongoing incident at an organization with multiple disparate branches and centralized security operations might require updating numerous firewalls from different vendors in many locations. This can be addressed in multiple ways, such as either manually configuring each firewall by remotely accessing the target devices and updating the required rules, or utilizing a GUI-based solution that allows the configuration of different devices from different vendors with the use of APIs. Standardized interfaces that utilize a common language for command and control would allow updating the firewalls in machine time by issuing only a single command. The command itself should be agnostic of the underlying device that will consume it but it should be function-relevant. The device itself remains responsible for understanding the command issued in a common language and format, and executing it.

The aforementioned shortcomings in traditional cyber defense approaches and the identified requirements for enabling coordinated cyber response in cyber-relevant time motivated the development of OpenC2. Open Command and Control (OpenC2) is a suite of specifications that enable command and control of cyber defense systems and components at machine speed and in a manner that is agnostic of the overall underlying technologies utilized. OpenC2 aims to standardize the way cyber defense systems and functions communicate and consequently interoperate in a way that security automation and orchestration become feasible and less complex to achieve.

Concisely, the suite of specifications includes the language specification, actuator profiles, and transfer specifications. The OpenC2 language specification provides the semantics for the essential elements of the language, the structure for commands and responses, and defines the proper compositions and data types for the language elements that represent the command or response. OpenC2 actuator profiles extend and specify subsets of the OpenC2 language relevant to particular cyber defense functions. Examples of cyber defense functions include stateless and stateful packet filtering. Actuator profiles also provide the appropriate conformance requirements and recommendations for enabling interoperability between different technologies. The OpenC2 transfer specifications utilize existing protocols and standards for encoding and communicating OpenC2 messages securely.

The rest of the paper introduces and delves into the mechanics of OpenC2 and presents a use case implementation.

2. Open command and control – OpenC2

OpenC2 (OASIS, 2019) is developed by a domain-expert technical committee within the OASIS international standards body. The

National Security Agency of the United States Department of Defense, the Bank of America, and the University of Oslo, to name a few, are among many organizations and agencies globally that support the effort and offer expertise for its successful development (OpenC2 involves members from industry, government, and academia). The Organization for the Advancement of Structured Information Standards¹ (OASIS) is a global nonprofit consortium that drives the development, convergence, and adoption of many open standards for the global information society.

2.1. OpenC2 scope

Real-time detection and mitigation of threats at every tier in every cyber environment require the integration, synchronization, and automation of sensing, sense-making, decision-making, and acting capabilities by secure automated orchestration and the development of messaging and C2 infrastructure standards (Herring and Willett, 2014).

A high-level decomposition of the functional blocks within a cyber-defense ecosystem or a single advanced system includes:

- Sensing: collection of data from sensors with the intent to provide awareness.
- Sense-making: analytics to provide understanding in a particular context and the current state based on the collected data.
- Decision-making: selection of response actions relevant to the current state.
- Responding/Acting: execution of a selected course of action to mitigate, remediate, or further investigate a situation as indicated by a response plan. This can be a mix of automated and manual actions integrating human in the loop.
- Message Fabric: assured communications infrastructure to ensure a standard communication medium for all the technologies involved, and seamless execution of commands in a timely manner by authenticated and authorized entities.

The above, also known as Integrated Adaptive Cyber Defense (Willett, 2015), is analogous to the classic OODA control loop (observe, orient, decide, and act) but tailored to cybersecurity operations with the purpose of promoting and leveraging automation in cyber defense. The OODA loop is a military approach for disrupting effectively and timely adversarial operations by iteratively collecting and processing information for making the right decisions and acting at a faster pace than the adversaries.

OpenC2 addresses the response (acting) segment of cyber defense, also known as course of action. Course of action refers to measures that can be taken to prevent or respond to attacks (Mavroeidis and Bromander, 2017). The defined language enables unambiguous machine-to-machine communication and is agnostic of any particular transfer or transport protocol, and information assurance implementation. Other aspects of coordinated cyber response such as sensing, sense-making (analytics), and selecting appropriate courses of action are beyond the scope of OpenC2 but are required to enable coordinated cyber response in cyber-relevant time. Thus, OpenC2 assumes that the rest of the functional blocks are in place.

2.2. OpenC2 terminology

This section elucidates terminology pertinent to OpenC2.

- Action: a single task to be performed. An action (e.g., deny, update, contain, restart) is an instruction from a producer to a consumer and is executed by an actuator (e.g., stateful or stateless packet filter).

¹ <https://www.oasis-open.org>.

Fig. 1. OpenC2 message exchange.

Command Matrix					
	Allow	Deny	Query	Delete	Update
ipv4_connection	●	●			
ipv6_connection	●	●			
ipv4_net	●	●			
ipv6_net	●	●			
features			●		
slpf/rule_number				●	
file					●

Fig. 2. OpenC2 SLPF command matrix.

- Target: the object of the action. An action is performed on a target (e.g., IP address, file, process, device).
- Argument: a property that provides additional granularity with respect to how, when, and where to perform a command (e.g., date, time, periodicity, duration, specific interface). Arguments are context-dependant (action-target pair dependant).
- Specifier: a property or field that identifies a target or actuator to some level of precision.
- Actuator: the function performed by the consumer that executes the command (e.g., stateless or stateful packet filtering). An actuator is defined within the context of an actuator profile.
- Actuator Profile: a subset of the OpenC2 language relevant to a specific cyber defense function. An actuator profile may extend the OpenC2 language by defining targets, command arguments, and specifiers that are relevant and/or unique to a specific actuator function.
- Command: a message defined by an action-target pair and possibly additional arguments and specifiers that is sent from a producer, received by a consumer, and executed by an actuator.
- Response: a message from a consumer to a producer acknowledging a command or returning the requested resources or status based on a previously received command.
- Message: a content- and transport-independent set of elements conveyed between producers and consumers.
- Producer: an entity (device, application, functional block) that generates and sends commands. Note that a single entity can have both producer and consumer capabilities.

- Consumer: an entity (device, application, functional block) that receives and possibly acts upon commands. Note that a single entity can have both consumer and producer capabilities and support multiple actuator functions.

2.3. OpenC2 overview

OpenC2 aims to enable coordinated defense in cyber-relevant time between decoupled blocks that perform cyber defense functions. The assumption that underlies the design of OpenC2 is that the sensing and analytics for sense-making have been provisioned and the decision to act has been made. OpenC2 was designed based on the following four principles:

- Technology Agnostic: the OpenC2 language defines a set of unbiased abstract and atomic cyber defense actions, enabling interoperability among cyber defense systems independently of any other aspects of the underlying implementations.
- Concise: the OpenC2 language is minimal, focusing only on the essential information needed to derive targeted cyber defense actions. The language is designed to provide minimum overhead in the communication of OpenC2 messages and is appropriate for network constrained environments.
- Abstract: OpenC2 commands and responses are defined abstractly and can be encoded and transferred via multiple schemes as dictated by the needs of different implementation environments.

Fig. 3. Architecture with native OpenC2 interfaces.

Fig. 4. Architecture with OpenC2 proxy (middleware).

- Extensible: the OpenC2 language should evolve alongside cyber defense technologies. Supported by the aforementioned design principles OpenC2 can be extended for introducing new cyber defense functionality.

OpenC2 uses a request-response paradigm where a command is generated and encoded by a producer and transferred to a consumer using a secure transfer protocol (Fig. 1).

The consumer normally executes the received command and can respond to a producer with the status of the execution and other requested information. A producer can adjust its behavior based on the capability (supported features) of a consumer. In particular, a producer can request details about which versions of OpenC2 language, actuator profiles, and action-target pairs a consumer supports. The capability definitions can be easily extended in a non-centralized manner, allowing standard and non-standard capabilities to be defined with semantic and syntactic rigor. It needs to be emphasized that not all targets are meaningful in the context of a specific action. Although a command such as “update ipv4_connection” may be syntactically valid, the combination does not reflect an operation supported by a particular actuator profile. For example, the actuator profile for Stateless Packet Filtering (SLPF) version 1.0 (Brule et al., 2019) defines only one target, namely “file”, relevant to the action “update” (Fig. 2). Consumers and producers must satisfy the requirements specified in the lan-

guage specification and relevant actuator profile(s) to claim conformance. Compliance with the conformance clauses enables interoperability, the ability of a system to operate in conjunction with other systems.

2.4. OpenC2-enabled functionality and integration

As OpenC2 evolves and matures through additions, updates, adoption, and testing, we expect more vendors to introduce native support. A native OpenC2 interface is a capability that allows systems and functions to be called and managed directly by other systems or functions using the OpenC2 language, enabling interoperability and eliminating the need for any middleware. Cyber defense systems that natively support OpenC2 can produce or consume OpenC2 commands without the need of any translation service for interpreting the commands to the consumer proprietary language and syntax. This approach shifts the interface engineering complexity, conformance testing, and maintenance at the vendors’ side compared to approaches that demand middleware to perform translations, such as proxies that are also most of the time community-based software efforts. An example architecture with OpenC2 interfaces is presented in Fig. 3, where producers and consumers communicate natively, eliminating the multidimensional complexity and the computing and network overhead any additional translation technology would introduce.

As observed in Fig. 3, an orchestrator serves as a mission manager that issues or forwards OpenC2 commands to consumer actuators. Defining orchestrator architectures or technology is out of the scope of OpenC2. However, an orchestrator should be able to send, receive, and keep track of OpenC2 commands and responses, register and authenticate devices and functions, deal with certificate management, and may support multiple serializations and transfer protocols. In cases where cyber defense systems do not natively support OpenC2, integration is achieved by introducing middleware technology, such as a proxy, that does the appropriate translation/mapping from OpenC2 to the relevant vendor-proprietary notation and maybe act as a messaging infrastructure (Fig. 4). The positioning of the technologies in Figs. 3 and 4 is notional for aiding the understanding of the reader and do not represent factual architectures.

2.5. OpenC2 serialization

Serialization is the process of converting an object into stream of bytes so that it can be stored or transferred over a network. Its main purpose is to save the state of an object (in our case, an OpenC2 command or response) in a standard format that can be transferred, reconstructed, and understood by any other application or system that supports the same serialization. The OpenC2 language is agnostic of any particular serialization format; however, implementations must support JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) in accordance with RFC 7493 (Bray, 2015) and additional requirements as to how OpenC2 data types are represented in JSON. For instance, an OpenC2 data type “IPv4-Addr” that specifies an Internet Protocol address version 4 must be a JSON string containing the “dotted-quad” representation of an IPv4 address as specified in RFC 2673, Section 3.2 (Crawford, 1999). An OpenC2 data type “MAC-Addr” that represents a media access control address must be a JSON string containing the text representation of a MAC address in colon hexadecimal format as defined in IEEE Standards Association (2018). The syntax of an OpenC2 command in JSON is presented below.

```
{
  "action": <action type>,
  "target": {
    <target type>: {
      <target specifiers as key:value
        pairs>}},
  "args": {
    <general command arguments as key:
      value pairs>,
    <actuator type>: {
      <actuator-relevant command
        arguments as key:value pairs>}},
  "actuator": {
    <actuator type>: {
      <actuator specifiers as key:value
        pairs>}}
}
```

Reflecting on a use case where a sandbox and a firewall are part of an orchestration process (using a security playbook), identified malicious C2 infrastructure, such as IPs related to malware, could be forwarded to the orchestrator and from the orchestrator to the consumer. The orchestrator knowing the actuator’s capability, which in our case is a firewall device, will populate and forward precise OpenC2 commands that can block the target IPs. The

commands are expressed in JSON, transferred as 1’s and 0’s in the wire, and reconstructed back to JSON for processing and consumption by the indicated actuator. An OpenC2 command relevant to the described use case is presented below.

```
{
  "action": "deny",
  "target": {
    "ipv4_net": "malicious C2"
  },
  "args": {
    "response_requested": "complete"
  },
  "actuator": {
    "slpf": {
      "hostname": "firewall-01"
    }
  }
}
```

The command defines a “deny” action that blocks an IPv4 address (target) expressed in CIDR notation (classless inter-domain routing), requests a response message about the status and maybe the results of the performed command by the actuator, and specifies the actuator that will perform the requested action. A response indicating that the actuator successfully issued the command is presented right below, where according to the OpenC2 Language Specification version 1.0 in a response message, a response code is required, and a status text is optional.

```
{
  "status": 200,
  "status_text": "OK"
}
```

Consumers support one or more actuator profiles and possibly more than one serialization formats (e.g., JSON and CBOR) based on their capability. The command above is populated based on the Stateless Packet Filtering (SLPF) version 1.0 actuator profile supported by “firewall-01”. On that basis, both consumers and producers should fulfill the actuator-specific requirements annotated in the relevant specification for successfully inter-communicating and interpreting the messages. For example, when the mask of an “ipv4_net” target is unspecified, it must be treated as a single IPv4 address. Additionally, the address range specified in the “ipv4_net” must be treated as a source or destination address. The exact serialization format used for message exchange is annotated and included in the header of a message.

2.6. OpenC2 language

The OpenC2 language is described in the Open Command and Control (OpenC2) Language Specification document, currently, in version 1.0 (Romano and Sparrell, 2019). The language, as described in Section 2.3, is designed to be technology agnostic, concise, abstract and extensible, and is used to compose messages for command and control of cyber defense systems and components. The OpenC2 language is used in conjunction with OpenC2 actuator profiles that extend the language in the context of particular cyber defense functions (discussed in Section 2.7), and OpenC2 transfer specifications that provide guidance on how OpenC2 messages should be transferred over specific transfer protocols (discussed in Section 2.8). The language specification formalizes the

OpenC2 Actions (Defined in the Language Specification)	
Name	Description
allow	permit access or execution of a target
cancel	invalidate a previously issued action
contain	isolate a file, process, or entity so that it cannot modify or access assets or processes
delete	remove an entity (e.g., data, files, flows)
deny	prevent a certain event or action from completion, such as preventing a flow from reaching a destination or preventing access
detonate	execute and observe the behavior of a target (e.g., file, hyperlink) in an isolated environment
investigate	task the recipient to aggregate and report information as it pertains to a security event or incident
locate	find an object physically, logically, functionally, or by organization
query	initiate a request for information
restart	stop then start a system or an activity
scan	systematic examination of some aspect of the entity or its environment
start	initiate a process, application, system, or activity
stop	halt a system or end an activity

Fig. 5. Subset of OpenC2 actions defined in the language specification.

most common actions and targets relevant to cyber defense functions and defines command arguments for additional granularity. Furthermore, the specification elaborates on the available target and data types, includes serialization and encoding requirements, and presents examples of commands and responses in JSON. Examples of common actions and targets can be seen in Figs. 5 and 6.

As observed in Fig. 6, OpenC2 targets may be further refined by target type definitions that represent the combination of properties that make up a target, and specify their custom format attributes which are accurately described by authoritative resources, be they RFCs or other external specifications. For example, the target “file” is of target type “File”. The target type “File” is the combination of “name”, “path”, and “hashes” properties, that are of types “String”, “String”, and “Hashes”, respectively. The defined data type “Hashes” can be “md5”, “sha1”, or “sha256” and are expressed in binary or hexadecimal. Also they should be semantically validated based on their authoritative definition in their respective RFCs (RFC 1321 (Rivest, 1992), RFC 6234 (Eastlake 3rd and Hansen, 2011), and RFC 6234 (Eastlake 3rd and Hansen, 2011)).

The language defines two payload structures: Command and Response. A command is an instruction from one system known as the producer to one or more systems known as the consumer(s) to act on the command’s content. A command is comprised of four main components, of which two are required, and two are optional. The required components are the action-target pair, and the optional components are the command arguments and the actuator specifiers. Command arguments influence a command by providing additional information on how, when, and where should be performed. Moreover, command arguments can be used to convey the need for acknowledgment or additional status information about the execution of a command. Actuator specifiers further identify an actuator to some level of precision, such as a specific actuator or a group of actuators. A command can also contain an optional command identifier for tracking and referencing

related commands and responses. The response is a message sent from the recipient of a command. Response messages provide acknowledgment, status, results of a query, or other requested information. At a minimum, a response will contain a status code to indicate the result of performing a command.

2.7. OpenC2 function-relevant profiles

Actuator profiles allow cyber defense systems to interoperate in the context of particular cyber defense functions. A cyber defense system that serves as OpenC2 consumer can support one or more profiles based on its capability. For instance, a firewall is a policy enforcement mechanism that restricts or permits traffic based on static values such as source and destination address, protocol, and ports. A firewall as a cyber defense function can permit stateless or stateful packet filtering, and it can be dedicated (hardware-based) or integrated into other technologies and devices for adding a layer of security (software-based), such as networking and end devices. The engineering decision of defining profiles that are function-centric rather than device-centric is based on the observation that profiles for devices tend to overlap (key/value repetition), with at times only a few of their properties being different. For example, devices and technologies that support stateless and stateful packet filtering, such as network firewalls, host firewalls, cloud-based firewalls, and proxy firewalls, to name a few, share common characteristics in terms of operation, management, and configuration, meaning that an individual profile for each device would be very similar if not identical in some cases. However, all the aforementioned devices and technologies support stateful packet filtering, resulting in the creation of one common profile for use.

An actuator profile (specification) is created using a subset of the general language, and it may also extend the language by defining additional actions, targets, command arguments, and

OpenC2 Targets (Defined in the Language Specification)		
Name	Type	Description
artifact	Artifact	an array of bytes representing a file-like object or a link to that object
command	String	a reference to a previously issued Command
device	Device	the properties of a hardware device
domain_name	Domain-Name	a network domain name
email_addr	Email-Addr	a single email address
features	Features	a set of items used with the query action to determine an actuator's capabilities
file	File	properties of a file
ipv4_connection	IPv4-Connection	a 5-tuple of source and destination IPv4 address ranges, source and destination ports, and protocol
ipv6_connection	IPv6-Connection	a 5-tuple of source and destination IPv6 address ranges, source and destination ports, and protocol
mac_addr	MAC-Addr	a Media Access Control (MAC) address - EUI-48 or EUI-64
process	Process	common properties of an instance of a computer program as executed on an operating system

Fig. 6. Subset of OpenC2 targets defined in the language specification.

actuator specifiers relevant to a particular cyber defense function. In addition, an actuator profile includes conformance rules and requirements for seamless communication between producers and consumers. Creating function-relevant profiles (actuator profiles) is an iterative process that demands stakeholder, and specifically, vendor support. Security vendors and other organizations create custom actuator profiles and integrate OpenC2 into their cyber defense products and operations (based on use cases relevant to their organization or industry) for testing purposes, but also for supporting the development of OpenC2 by providing prototypes and reference implementations, where their cyber defense technologies can consume commands natively. The OpenC2 technical committee evaluates where function-relevant custom actuator profiles cluster to drive the development of new standard actuator profiles.

A consumer may support multiple actuator profiles. As mentioned in Section 2.3, a producer can request information about the versions of OpenC2 language, actuator profiles, and action-target pairs a consumer supports. It is possible for a consumer to support a limited range of action-target pairs of a profile but still claim conformance with the actuator profile. An example query for requesting the capability of a consumer can be seen right below.

```
{
  "action": "query",
  "target": {
    "features": [
      "versions",
      "profiles",
      "pairs"
    ]
  }
}
```

An example response from a consumer providing the versions of OpenC2 language, actuator profiles, and action-target pairs supported can be seen right below.

```
{
  "status": 200,
  "results": {
    "versions": ["1.0"],
    "profiles": ["slpf-1.0"],
    "pairs": {
      "allow": ["ipv6_net"],
      "deny": ["ipv6_net"],
      "query": ["features"],
      "delete": ["slpf:rule_number"],
      "update": ["file"]
    }
  }
}
```

Each OpenC2 specification, including actuator profiles, possesses a unique name in the form of a URI used to identify the document. A unique name ensures that all objects are identifiable and unambiguously referenced. For the sake of brevity in this paper, only the Stateless Packet Filtering actuator profile (SLPF) version 1.0 is presented (Brule et al., 2019).

Actuator Profile for Stateless Packet Filtering (SLPF): a stateless packet filter allows or blocks specific traffic based on a defined set of security rules and does not consider traffic patterns, connection state, data flows, applications, or payload information. The SLPF profile specifies the set of actions, targets, specifiers, and command arguments that are relevant to stateless packet filtering functionality. Through this command set, cyber security orchestrators may gain visibility into and provide control over the SLPF functionality in a manner that is independent (agnostic) of the instance

Fig. 7. Overview of OpenC2 stateless packet filtering actuator profile.

Command Arguments Matrix					
	Allow target	Deny target	Query features	Delete slpf/rule_number	Update file
response_requested	●	●	●	●	●
start_time	●	●		●	●
stop_time	●	●			
duration	●	●			
persistent	●	●			
direction	●	●			
insert_rule	●	●			
drop_process		●			

Fig. 8. OpenC2 SLPF command arguments matrix.

(vendor-technology/device) of the SLPF function. A high-level overview of the SLPF actuator profile functionality is presented in Fig. 7.

Actuator profiles define the language extensions that are meaningful and possibly unique to the actuator. For example, as seen in Fig. 7, the SLPF profile defines multiple command arguments and one target introducing refined SLPF functionality in addition to the properties adopted from the language specification (OpenC2 properties from the general language specification that apply to SLPF). Fig. 2 presents the action-target combinations that are syntactically

valid when using the SLPF specification. Furthermore, Fig. 8 elucidates the command arguments supported by each action.

Briefly, the additional SLPF-defined target “rule_number” combined with the action “delete” removes existing rules from a firewall rule-set. Also, the SLPF command argument “persistent” designates whether new firewall rules are persistent or not. The “direction” argument specifies whether firewall rules apply to incoming traffic, outgoing traffic, or both. The command argument “insert_rule” is used to specify a rule number to a new entry. The argument “drop_process” defines how the actuator handles

Common Message Elements		
Name	Type	Description
content		message body as specified by content_type and msg_type
content_type	String	media type that identifies the format of the content, including major version. For example, when using HTTPS: application/openc2-cmd+json;version=1.0
msg_type	Message-Type	the type of OpenC2 message (command/response)
status	Status-Code	populated with a numeric status code in responses
request_id	String	a unique identifier created by the producer and copied by the consumer into all responses, in order to support reference to a particular command, transaction, or event chain
created	Date-Time	creation date/time of the content
from	String	authenticated identifier of the creator of a message or authority for execution of a message
to	ArrayOf(String)	authenticated identifier(s) of the authorized recipient(s) of a message

Fig. 9. Common message elements for transfer protocols.

denied packets. For example, an actuator can send a notification to the source of the packet or drop the traffic and send a false acknowledgment.

2.8. OpenC2 transfer specifications

A transfer specification defines how a particular transfer protocol is used for exchanging OpenC2 messages between producers and consumers. A transfer specification is agnostic of the content of a message, and similarly, the content of a message is agnostic of the underlying transfer protocol used. The language specification defines a set of message elements (Fig. 9) that can be represented and used within the headers of a transfer protocol or some of them potentially within the body of OpenC2 messages to ensure interoperability and robust message exchange between technologies.

According to conformance clauses one and twelve in the language specification, OpenC2 producers and consumers should support one or more OpenC2 transfer specifications, which identify underlying transport protocols that can provide authenticated, ordered, lossless delivery of uniquely identified OpenC2 messages. OpenC2 can be layered over any standard transfer and transport protocol. The transfer specifications utilize existing protocols and standards to implement OpenC2 in specific environments based on their requirements, capability, and constraints. An example is HTTP versus MQTT, where the first is recommended for fast and reliable networks, whereas the second is a better choice for networks that experience varying levels of latency due to occasional bandwidth constraints or unreliable connections. For the sake of brevity in this paper, only OpenC2 over HTTP(S) version 1.0 is presented (Lemire, 2019).

OpenC2 Messages over HTTP(S): the Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP) over Transport Layer Security (TLS) is one of the recommended transfer mechanisms for OpenC2 messages due to its broad availability and ability to transfer information in TCP/IP networks securely. OpenC2 over HTTP(S) is suitable for operational environments where connectivity is highly available and of sufficient bandwidth such that no appreciable message delays or dropped packets will be experienced.

The HTTP(S) Transfer Specification version 1.0 (Lemire, 2019) provides guidance on how to utilize HTTP and the Transport

Layer Security cryptographic protocol for exchanging OpenC2 messages. Each endpoint of an OpenC2 over HTTP interaction has both an OpenC2 role and an HTTP function. OpenC2 producers act as HTTP clients and transmit commands to consumers that act as HTTP listeners (server). A producer can issue OpenC2 commands using only the HTTP Post method, and a consumer can respond with an HTTP response message. As mentioned above, the OpenC2 language specification requires the use of two message elements for ensuring interoperability, namely “content_type” and “message_type”. When OpenC2 command messages are sent over HTTP, the message type is “request” (HTTP request), and the content type follows the syntax [application/openc2-cmd+[serialization];version=[version]], where the media type, the serialization format, and the major version of the OpenC2 language utilized, are specified. This approach is built on the mechanics used to generate the related HTTP Content-Type header. For example, an OpenC2 command in JSON and conformant with the OpenC2 Language Specification version 1.0 and the Specification for Transfer of OpenC2 Messages via HTTP(S) version 1.0 should populate an HTTP Content-Type header “application/openc2-cmd+json;version=1.0”. Equally, an OpenC2 response uses the message type “response” (HTTP response) and content type [application/openc2-rsp+[serialization];version=[version]].

Another considered approach that can provide a more transport-independent design to use the message elements over transfer protocols indistinctively is the inclusion of message elements into an OpenC2 construct that is part of the OpenC2 message body. This approach also has the benefit of being a better fit to transfer protocols that do not contain directly mappable headers or support custom ones.

According to the HTTP(S) Transfer Specification version 1.0, other header fields that SHOULD be populated when sending OpenC2 messages over HTTP are the “Cache-Control” that specifies what may be stored in caches on any of the systems engaged at an OpenC2 transaction, the HTTP X-Request-ID that accommodates the “request_id” string (defined in the OpenC2 language specification, see Fig. 9) populated by a producer, and “Date” that reflects the date and time at which the message was originated in the preferred IMF-fixdate format and conditions, as defined in Sections 7.1.1.1 and 7.1.1.2 of RFC 7231 (Fielding and Reschke, 2014). Furthermore, the specification specifies other header fields that

Fig. 10. Prototype Integration over DXL and HTTPS.

MUST be used when sending OpenC2 commands (HTTP request) over HTTP, such as the "Host" that specifies the hostname of the HTTP server and the listening port, the "Content-type" as described above, and the "Accept" header that advertises which content types, expressed as MIME types, the client is able to understand (e.g., "application/openc2-rsp+json;version=1.0").

The need for confidentiality, identification, and authentication when sending OpenC2 messages is addressed with the use of Transport Layer Security (TLS) cryptographic protocol. As stated in the HTTP(S) Transfer Specification version 1.0, OpenC2 endpoints must accept TLS version 1.2 connections or higher and must not support older TLS or Secure Sockets Layer (SSL) versions. The TLS sessions must not use NULL cipher suites because they do not provide confidentiality for the TLS traffic, and OpenC2 endpoints supporting TLS version 1.2 must not use any of the blacklisted cipher suites identified in Appendix A of RFC 7540 (Belshe et al., 2015). Finally, OpenC2 endpoints supporting TLS version 1.3 must not implement zero round trip time resumption (0-RTT) as it has been proved to be prone to replay attacks.

3. OpenC2 use case implementation and results

The use case presented in this section is a consolidated effort by the University of Oslo, AT&T, the University of North Carolina, and the Cyber Defense Institute of Japan to demonstrate interoperable tactical responses in cyber relevant time using OpenC2. We present a proof-of-concept implementation of OpenC2 across several systems and components that support stateless packet filtering. The four prototypes developed conform with the Stateless

Packet Filtering actuator profile version 1.0 and are all interfaces for different products that serve the same purpose.

The implementation comprises four integrated prototypes over two transfer protocols. In particular, the University of Oslo engineered an adapter that can utilize OpenC2 commands for device management and configuring firewall rules on Cisco routers that support access control lists. AT&T presented an adapter for configuring the packet filters of Amazon, Google, and Microsoft cloud platforms. The University of North Carolina developed an interface for configuring Linux iptables with OpenC2 commands. iptables is a command-line packet filtering utility that uses policy chains to allow or block traffic using the Netfilter framework provided by the Linux kernel. The Cyber Defense Institute of Japan created an OpenC2 interface for configuring firewalld. firewalld is a firewall tool for Linux operating systems. Like iptables, firewalld uses the kernel's Netfilter framework for filtering traffic. Fig. 10 presents a high-level diagram of the integration of the prototypes and the communication of OpenC2 messages.

The implementations communicated OpenC2 messages over the DXL (OpenDXL) message fabric and HTTPS. OpenDXL or Open Data Exchange Layer is a publish-subscribe message fabric that allows applications to publish and subscribe to message topics. An OpenC2 producer can publish an OpenC2 command on a relevant topic such as "network/packet-filters", and the producers can subscribe on the same topic to receive the published messages. A protocol bridge was created to facilitate message exchange for the implementations that were using an HTTP interface (listener) to communicate. The integration and message exchange would be more straightforward if an orchestrator has been used

for registering devices, and for certificate-based authentication management.

The experiments demonstrated and proved that OpenC2 enables command and control of cyber defense systems and components at machine speed and in a manner that is agnostic of the underlying technologies and protocols utilized. The integration confirmed that all prototypes could receive a single command (e.g., deny/block a particular IP address) and act on that command in the same way, proving that the language, the transfer specifications, and in particular the actuator profiles are robust enough to be used unambiguously among a set of different cyber defense systems and components of the same cyber defense function.

4. Conclusion

OpenC2 enables command and control of cyber defense components and systems in cyber-relevant time and in a manner that is agnostic of any of the underlying products, technologies, transfer mechanisms, or other implementation aspects. This is achieved by introducing a common language that allows seamless integration and enables interoperability between cyber defense technologies. OpenC2 cyber defense function-specific profiles (actuator profiles) can be integrated into cyber defense components and systems for introducing native OpenC2 interfaces, shifting traditional command and control approaches that are based on proprietary APIs (where a set of requirements that govern how one application can communicate and interact with another is provided), to an approach that response actions can be governed by one common language and be vendor agnostic. A language such as OpenC2 is necessary but insufficient to enable coordinated cyber responses that occur within cyber-relevant time. Other aspects of coordinated cyber response such as sensing, analytics, and selecting appropriate courses of action should be provisioned. OpenC2 will provide the capability of executing the chosen actions.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Vasileios Mavroeidis: Writing - original draft, Investigation, Validation, Writing - review & editing. **Joe Brule:** Writing - review & editing.

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² <https://www.oasis-open.org/committees/openc2>.